

1183-W grew better than isolate 283-P in both semisolid and liquid media (see figure).

Thirty-seven varieties and lines at early booting were inoculated in the field with infected rice grain culture of the two isolates. The infected grain was pressed, with slight wounding, onto the sheath tissue of the flag leaf of a tiller and attached with scotch tape. Disease severity or lesion length was measured at hard-dough to maturity.

Disease severity in genotypes differed. A significant isolate × variety interaction indicates the possibility that the isolates are distinct strains or races. Except for Kalarharsall, the difference in disease severity was not great. The mean disease severity of the 37 entries was significantly higher for isolate 283-P (13.1 cm) than for isolate 1183-W (11.4 cm), suggesting that 283-P is more virulent (see table). For these isolates, there was no relation between growth in culture media and virulence.

The mean disease severity based on lesion length shows that only one genotype, BR51-46-5-CI, may be considered moderately resistant (lesion length less than 6.5 cm); all others were moderately to highly susceptible (lesion length more than 6.5 cm). □

Reactions of 37 varieties and lines to 2 isolates of *Sarocladium oryzae* causing sheath rot of rice.

Variety or line	Mean length of lesion ^a (cm)	
	Isolate 283-P	Isolate 1183-W
B2489B-PN-1-76-8	24.0	21.6
BR51-46-5-C1	6.3	3.0
BR51-49-6-HR50	14.4	5.3
BR425-48-1-4-1-2-1	9.7	3.3
BR425-53-2-1-1-4-3	11.0	6.6
BR425-87-1-1-2-3-1	11.5	11.5
BR425-93-3-1-2-3-4	9.3	15.0
BR425-110-2-1-1-2-3	18.5	14.0
BR425-110-2-1-1-6-1	11.3	6.0
BR425-177-1-3-1-4-4	10.3	9.8
BR425-177-1-3-1-5-3	16.9	10.6
BR1242-6-1-1	15.0	9.2
BR1356-10-1-6	9.0	6.2
BR1356-13-2-1	19.8	13.0
BR1356-40-3-1	14.7	2.5
BR1356-40-4-4	8.7	7.5
BR1412-5-1-1	10.1	20.6
IR54	8.2	15.8
IR34	10.3	9.3
IR10781-75-3-2	18.3	15.4
IR17983-45-3-2-3-1	7.2	12.3
IR18047-3-2-1-3	9.5	11.8
IR25166-14-1-1	18.5	7.3
IR25173-2-5-2	12.8	10.4
IR25173-5-1-2	16.0	9.3
IR25177-3-1-2	16.0	9.0
Kachamota	10.0	14.2
Kalarharsall	4.3	18.0
KAU 2084	13.2	19.3
M12C-34-3	9.0	7.6
M61B-1-1-2	15.3	13.5
M61B-11-2-1	15.0	6.6
M61B-18-2-1	9.0	9.3
M66B-30-1	14.8	13.5
Ptb-18	17.5	10.2
RNR74229	19.8	21.5
RP1125-104-2-1-1	20.5	19.8
Mean	13.1	11.4

^aMeans of 3 replications. LSD for comparing means: (a) Isolates within a variety = 15.9 at P .05, (b) Varieties within an isolate = 5.9 at P .05, (c) Isolates among all varieties = 1.0 at P .05.

Studies on ratoon performance of leaf blast-susceptible varieties at ARS, Ponnampet, Karnataka

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In the National Screening Nursery (NSN) of 1985-86 kharif, 50 rice cultures were screened for reaction to leaf blast (BL). None of the cultures were resistant to leaf or neck BL; ratings varied from 7 to 9 cm on a 0-9 scale, with practically no yield.

The culms of the diseased entries were cut 10-15 cm from the base of the

Performance of main crop and ratoon crop of promising cultures in Mandya, India.

Variety	Main crop				Ratoon crop			
	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	BI rating		Yield (t/ha)	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Yield (t/ha)
			Leaf B1	Neck B1 (%)				
IET9667	86	133	2	90	0	36	99	1.7
IET9668	89	125	0	100	0	38	96	1.7
IET9670	94	114	1	90	0.1	41	91	1.6
Intan (check)	115	87	7	90	0	Ratoon crop destroyed by leaf B1		

^aThe test varieties had neither leaf nor neck BL.

plant and allowed to ratoon. Only 3 of the 50 cultures gave rise to productive tillers. These cultures were free from B1 and yielded, an average 1.6 t/ha. In the

ratoon, plant height was reduced 46.6% and days to flowering 42.6% (see table). □